

New Technologies for Mobile Salesforce Management

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How to cite this paper: Suraj C. Patil "New Technologies for Mobile Salesforce Management" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-3 | Issue-4, June 2019, pp.571-572, URL: <https://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd23663.pdf>

IJTSRD23663

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Salesforce have its name in both New York Stock Exchange (NYSE) and S&P 500 index. In year 2004, in it's IPO the company had raised approximately \$110 million in funding. Now it has much more of worth. Salesforce is always introducing new technologies and growing at top.

2. Literature Survey

Our study included different technologies introduced by salesforce for mobile salesforce management like App cloud, Apex, Lightning. The CRM process is followed everywhere in salesforce. CRM is already well defined by salesforce and it is implemented in mobile applications too. While we are living with one mobile phone per person it makes sense to include salesforce in mobile applications too because mobile is the next frontier in computing.

3. Mobile Salesforce

Apart from CRM, salesforce provides following services on its platform:

- Sales Cloud
- Marketing Cloud
- Community Cloud
- App Cloud
- Commerce Cloud
- Service Cloud

Following are technologies used in Salesforce platform:

- Apex
- Visualforce
- Lightning

3.1 App cloud

Salesforce app cloud is a platform as a service while developing mobile apps. It provides all CRM services to

ABSTRACT

We are living in a world where technology advances day by day and modern salesforce continue to evolve. We can apply modern CRM system to increase the ability to manage selling relationships. By referring this document, you will learn recent technologies to build goodwill with customer.

Keywords: Sales Force Automation, Salesforce.com, Microsoft, Mobile, CRM, Salesforce

1. INTRODUCTION

Not only delivering a successful product to customer but also having interaction with customer on the same platform and identifying their needs to make a good bond with them is a goal of salesforce. The central goal of salesforce is CRM (Customer Relationship Management). Salesforce has changed the way to deliver and use of enterprise software by changing the industry forever.

Salesforce is cloud based and does not need to set up by professionals. Also it is not much expensive, no maintenance and we can work with it from any device with active internet connection. Salesforce make CRM easy to use for small scale as well as large scale businesses. By using this approach, salesforce is world's number 1 CRM system. Apart from CRM, salesforce enables you to manage needs of customers by having interaction with them to make your organisation grow and succeed. Salesforce also called as Customer Success Platform.

mobile apps. Developers using frameworks in modern languages and business admins using drag and drop lightning tools like app builder and process builder can all leverage app cloud. You can run your apps on a secure infrastructure trusted by the world's leading brands easily scaling across every device from a bunch of users to lakhs instantly.

3.2 Apex

Apex is a programming language used in salesforce development. It is provided by Force.com. It is similar to C# and Java. It is a strongly-typed, case-insensitive, object-oriented programming language which has dot-notation and curly-brackets syntax. The basic purpose of Apex code is to express business logic and not to build user interface for interaction. Apex code can be reusable. Compatibility, scalability and maintenance of code is responsibility of Salesforce itself.

3.3 Lightning

Lightning is a platform for front end Salesforce. It is introduced in 2014. This framework is used to build Salesforce mobile app while customer can also able to build on it.

4. Choosing Right Tool

As far as mobile salesforce is concerned, used technologies are App cloud, Apex, Lightning. Other technologies are also used but these technologies come into focus when we use term mobile salesfoce.

There are many mobile salesforce automation tools in market. Companies shouldn't rush into choosing a right tool. Instead, they should consider their working team as a base

for tool. The goal of mobile Salesforce automation tool is to give the tools and information needed for working on devices like smartphones and tablets.

5. Growth of Salesforce

Salesforce was called as “the ant at the picnic” which was introduced by a CEO of small startup organisation Marc Benioff back in 2000. No one thought that this Salesforce would give a giant competition to other software companies. Benioff paid actors to carry “anti software” signs. They performed in a user conference for Siebel Systems, which used to sell CRM software. Later that, he hosted a military-themed party in which guests threw “pieces of software” into trash bins.

The stunts gained attention. And Salesforce got another name by business insider. The ant at the picnic has helped to create a \$250 billion global market. Benioff’s company was

built around one main idea: that software should be delivered 24/7 to people over the cloud. Salesforce was the first company to do this. In the late 1990s, companies like Oracle and SAP were selling software to businesses that had to be installed and updated on-premise. Now, Oracle, SAP, and the rest of the world are belatedly building cloud products, trying to catch on to the movement that Salesforce started.

6. Future of Salesforce developers:

We have a question in mind that what kind of Salesforce jobs and career opportunities exist for a fresher as well as someone looking to enhance their knowledge in the Salesforce. The answer depends on your expertise and what exactly you want to do. The Salesforce job market has ample opportunities for everyone right from Business Analyst, System Administrator, and Salesforce developer.

There are many organizations who are investing in Salesforce to shift from IT to cloud and CRM is performing greatly in every sector. Salesforce Customers, System Partners, Media, Federal Projects and Nonprofit organizations are using SFDC. Giants like Dell Inc, Pandora, Accenture, Deloitte, Cloud Sherpa’s are clients of SFDC.

It is loud and clear that how learning Salesforce can change your entire career graph and job security can pop- in with a wide area to cover due to Advanced SFDC Developer and Lightning. Salesforce is going to stay as every industry need data safety and Cloud is the safe answer as of now.

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